

1 Surface enhanced Raman scattering (SERS)-active
2 bacterial detection by layer-by-layer (LbL) assembly
3 all-nanoparticle microcapsules

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14 **ABSTRACT:** Polymeric microcapsules composed by the layer-by-layer (LbL) approach have
15 been used for various applications including drug delivery into cells and *in vivo*, conducting
16 enzyme catalyzed reactions, performing sensoric functions. Typically, LbL-assembled
17 microcapsules have been formulated via alternating deposition of positively and negatively
18 charged polyelectrolytes onto sacrificial templates or so-called cores. In this work, we extend the
19 LbL assembly to produce microcapsules solely based on nanoparticles instead of polymers. Both
20 gold and silver nanoparticles have been deposited as oppositely charged layers in the LbL
21 assembly. We have identified that 5 layers of nanoparticles is the minimum number of layers for
22 a stable assembly of capsules on calcium carbonate templates. Subsequently, the composite
23 capsules comprised of nanoparticles were applied as Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS)
24 platform, where the nanoparticle-based shell of capsules is shown to enable SERS of both solutes
25 and macromolecular structures such as bacterial cells.

27 Graphical Abstract

29 **Keywords:** polyelectrolyte, multilayer, LbL, capsules, SERS, bacterial

30

31 **1. Introduction**

32 In the recent years, application of polymeric micro- and nano- capsules has been steadily growing.
33 In the general area of polymeric microcapsules, those assembled by the layer-by-layer (LbL)
34 technique are particularly interesting due to flexibility of their design and a variety of stimuli,
35 which can be used for controlling their assembly and their properties.[1–3]
36 The LbL capsules have been introduced in the late 90-ies, while subsequently, encapsulation
37 methods have been developed, including pH-based method,[4] temperature-based method,[5]
38 encapsulation into templates,[6,7] while pH-based method is also used in the presence of enzymes
39 (biodegradability).[8–10] In many applications, the shell of capsules and even cells is
40 functionalized with nanoparticles, which could serve as “hot spots” for absorbing the respective
41 external stimuli such as electromagnetic light waves in the case of laser-based release,[11–14]
42 magnetic fields in the case of magnetic field-based activation,[15] and sound waves in the case of
43 ultrasound.[16] In initially demonstrated release using ultrasound very high ultrasound intensities
44 were used.[17] But substantial progress has taken place and the intensities necessary for
45 microcapsule activation and opening substantially decreased.[18] An essential reduction of
46 necessary ultrasound intensity was achieved by adsorbing or synthesizing in situ nanoparticles in
47 the shell of polymeric capsules, for example, SiO₂ nanoparticles on the capsule shells.[19,20]
48 Nanoparticles have been already incorporated into the layers of microcapsules,[21] but the
49 assembly was mainly done sequentially with polymers.[22–29] LbL layers of alternative
50 deposition of SiO₂ and TiO₂ nanoparticles has led to effective antireflection coatings, but SiO₂
51 were used as stacks for essentially smaller TiO₂ nanoparticles.[30] Nanoparticle adsorption on the
52 surfaces has resulted to an enhanced surface plasmon Raman resonance enhancement.[28,31–34]
53 Meanwhile different interfaces, where nanoparticles were used as surfactants have also been

54 considered by B. Binks.[35] Using solely nanoparticles as surfactants to build novel nanoscale
55 platform has been reported by M. Haase[36] via oil-in-water emulsion approach. Developing a
56 novel solely nanoparticle-based approach to capsule preparation would be promising in different
57 fields such as those where the presence of polymers is either not required or even can or should be
58 avoided.

59 Polyelectrolyte multilayer capsules have become powerful tools for different biomedical
60 applications including drug delivery, theranostic and biosensing.[37] Especially, sensor and bio-
61 sensor related applications have been used for different,[38] so it would be logical to aim
62 developing a sensor based on capsules for detection of molecules. One candidate for such sensor-
63 mechanisms involving nanoparticles is Surface-Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS), where the
64 fields, and as a result, scattering by molecules, is amplified due to plasmonic effect on
65 nanoparticles.

66 It is very promising to design the carrier with a dual even multiple functionality such as: delivery
67 function, sensorics function and theranostics[39]. For this reason the functionalization of the
68 carrier with plasmonic nanoparticles on the shell could provide the detection function for such
69 carrier.[40] For example, among these reported lectures, silver and gold nanoparticles were
70 common involved as enhancers.[41–43]

71 Various functionalized porous carriers, such as calcium carbonate porous template,[44–46]
72 hydroxyapatite[47] and silica particles[48], will enhance the detection ability by 6 order of
73 magnitude. Other than the porous carrier the polymeric capsules with as a SERS platform also
74 developed. Polyelectrolyte capsules[38] and the alginate hydrogel capsules[49] demonstrate
75 possibility not only release substance under the ultrasound but also provide the amplification inside
76 the *C-elegance*[50]. The microcapsules made of polymeric and metallic nanoparticles are also

77 suitable for performing label-free detection by SERS micro-spectroscopy.[51,52] In another
78 study,[53] RNA detection using polymeric microcapsules with encapsulated gold nanoparticles
79 has been made and presented. Furthermore, pH and carbamide sensing have been also realized
80 using SERS.[54,55]

81 The colloidal and chemical instability of nanoparticles may lead to a decreased intensity of the
82 received SERS signal,[56] while their controlled aggregation of nanoparticles[57] or waveguide
83 design[58] allow for a significant enhancement of the SERS signal. Furthermore, new approaches
84 for development of SERS-based diagnostic platforms are currently pursued, including waveguide-
85 based designs[58] and fiber[59,60].

86 SERS platforms have been applied in different fields including: in cell biology[57,61,62] and
87 biomolecules[53,63,64] and environment.[65,66] SERS detection of molecules using
88 microcapsules represents a different approach compared to using nanoparticles alone for detection
89 of molecules. This is particularly noticeable for detection of, for example, exosomes[67–69] and
90 bacteria[70,71]. Meanwhile, accurate, fast, simple and sensitive method of detection of
91 microorganisms, such as *Escherichia coli*, which is involved in nosocomial, waterborne and
92 foodborne infectious diseases, are important for food safety and human health care.[72]
93 Accordingly, there has always been a strong driving force to develop a rapid, simple, and efficient
94 method for bacterial cell detection with SERS application.

95 Most of the microcapsules are hybrid, which contained organic and inorganic components. But the
96 PEM microcapsules has a number of drawbacks such as material consuming and laborious process
97 of synthesis, high permeability to small molecules, low reproducibility, aggregation and unknow
98 long-term stability frequently using the synthetic polymers.[73] For this reason to design a novel

99 types of microcapsules based on inorganic components with capability to enhance the Raman
100 signal still represents a significant challenge.

101 In this work, we have assembled one new type of microcapsules purely composed of nanoparticles
102 in an aqueous solution. Sequential adsorption of silver and gold nanoparticles has been carried out,
103 where silver nanoparticles were synthesized in situ, while gold nanoparticles have been added
104 upon sequential build-up of the layers of silver/gold capsules. The LbL assembly of nanoparticles
105 has been carried out on calcium carbonate templates, which were subsequently removed forming
106 the hollow capsules comprised of nanoparticles. Scanning electron microscopy analysis has been
107 performed to examine the capsule structure. The constructed capsules have been applied as a SERS
108 platform which achieved rapid detection of standard molecules and microorganisms.

109

110 2. Materials and methods

111 2.1 Materials

112 Gold(III) chloride trihydrate (HAuCl_4 , $\geq 99.9\%$), D-(+)-Glucose ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$, 180.16 Da, $\geq 99.5\%$),
113 Tetraoctylammonium bromide (TOAB, $[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_7]_4\text{N}(\text{Br})$, 98%), Toluene (99.8%), Sodium
114 sulfate anhydrous (Na_2SO_4 , $> 99.0\%$), 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP, $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2$, $\geq 99\%$),
115 Sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3 , $\geq 99.5\%$), Calcium chloride (CaCl_2 , $\geq 93.0\%$), Ammonium hydroxide
116 solution (28.0-30.0% NH_3 basis), Silver nitrate (AgNO_3 , $> 99\%$), Sodium borohydride (NaBH_4 ,
117 99%) and Rhodamine 6G (dye content $\sim 95\%$, 479.01 Da) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. In
118 all experiments, Milli-Q water with resistivity higher than $18.2 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}$ was used.

119 2.2 Particle Synthesis

120 Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) were synthesized via the modified protocol of Gittins[74] as follows.
121 30 mL of 30 mM HAuCl_4 was added to 80 mL solution of 25 mM tetraethylammonium bromide
122 in toluene. 25 mL freshly prepared NaBH_4 was added to the mixture and stirred for 30 min. After
123 that, two phases were split and the organic phase was subsequently washed with 0.1 M H_2SO_4 0.1
124 M NaOH , and H_2O for three times, afterwards dried with anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . Last, 0.1 M DMAP
125 solution with a ratio of 1:1 was used to transfer AuNPs in prepared nanoparticle mixtures into
126 aqueous solution.

127 Spherical calcium carbonate microparticle core was fabricated via a modified previous reported
128 protocol.[75] 1 mL of Na_2CO_3 (0.33 M) was loaded into a 100 mL glass beaker, then an equal
129 volume of CaCl_2 (0.33 M) was injected rapidly and stirred at 600 rpm for 1 min. The color of the

130 mixture solution became milky-white immediately after mixing. The synthesized CaCO_3 particles
131 were carefully washed with 70% ethanol and dried for whole night at 100 °C.

132 5% $[\text{Ag}(\text{NH}_3)_2]\text{OH}$ solution, also known as Tollens' reagent, was obtained by adding 0.5 M
133 ammonium hydroxide to 0.5 M AgNO_3 dropwise until the complex solution become transparent.

134 **2.3 Capsule synthesis**

135 To produce 4 bilayers silver and gold microcapsules, 10 mg of CaCO_3 microparticle powder was
136 placed in a 2 mL Eppendorf tube and dissolved in 1 mL of deionized water. The classic silver
137 mirror reaction[45] was conducted on the CaCO_3 core to form the first layer. A total of 200 μL of
138 fresh Tollens' reagent and 200 μL D-glucose were injected into the tube and was left on stirring
139 for one hour. After that, silver nanoparticle coated CaCO_3 microparticles were washed three times
140 by water. After washing steps, 1 mL as-prepared AuNPs were added and stirred for 15 minutes for
141 the fabrication of the next layer after 3 minutes of the ultrasound treatment. Wash the sediment
142 and repeat with AuNPs for second layer until the supernatant shows red color to confirm the
143 formation of nanoparticles. EDTA solution with a concentration of 0.2 M at pH 7 was added to
144 remove the sacrificial CaCO_3 core. Further, excessive EDTA salt was removed by washing with
145 deionized water several times.

146 **2.4 Bacteria preparation and growth**

147 For experiments with bacteria the strain of *Escherichia coli* TOP10 was used with genetic
148 properties: F⁻ mcrA Δ (mrr-hsdRMS-mcrBC) Φ 80lacZ Δ M15 Δ lacX74 recA1 araD139 Δ (ara leu)
149 7697 galU galK rpsL (StrR) endA1 nupG. Bacterial suspension was obtained from the stationary
150 overnight culture grown on NB1 medium (Carl Roth) at 37 °C on a rotary shaker with preset at

151 150 rpm. To wash out the media components we centrifuged 50ml culture at 5000g for 5 min and
152 resuspended in 30 mL sterile 0.9% NaCl or Milli-Q water. Washing was repeated 3 more times.
153 Finally, cells were resuspended in 1ml and frozen at -20 °C after addition of 10% glycerol. Before
154 experiments, cells were thawed and washed one more time to wash out any cell debris as well as
155 glycerol.

156 **2.5 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)**

157 The morphology of the surface-modified particles and capsules both were examined in a scanning
158 electron microscope (JEOL JSM 7100F SEM, JEOL Ltd., Japan). To study the fabrication process
159 of the microcapsules, aliquots which own different quantity of layers for each type of
160 microcapsules were taken for SEM.

161 **2.6 X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)**

162 The XRD patterns of the samples were recorded using a powder X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku
163 MiniFlex, Rigaku Ltd., Japan) with Cu-K α radiation (40 kV, 15 mA, NiCK β -filter, 1.5406 Å) in
164 the 2 Θ angle range from 20 to 80° with a scanning step of 0.01° and a rate of 7°/min. Data were
165 evaluated using the integrated X-ray powder diffraction software SmartLab Studio II and Database
166 pdf4.

167 **2.7 Raman Spectroscopy**

168 Raman spectra were acquired on a Raman microscope (Alpha300, WiTec GmbH, Germany) with
169 785 nm NIR (near-infrared) laser. To test the performance of substrates for surface enhancement
170 Raman spectroscopy (SERS), Rhodamine 6G water solution (10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , and 10^{-5} M) was used as
171 an analyte. All SERS maps ($30 \times 25 \mu\text{m}$) of R6G with concentrations of 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} and 10^{-5} M,

172 were recorded using a Nikon 40×/ 0.6 NA objective with laser power of 16 mW and integration
173 time of 5 seconds per spectrum. Enhancement factors (EF) were calculated according to the
174 formula:

$$EF = \frac{I_{SERS}}{I_{Raman}} \cdot \frac{p_{Raman}}{p_{SERS}} \cdot \frac{c_{Raman}}{c_{SERS}} \quad (1)$$

175 where I_{SERS} and I_{Raman} are intensities of the SERS amplified signal and initial signal of the control
176 analyte; p_{SERS} and p_{Raman} are laser power for SERS spectra and control analyte; c_{SERS} and c_{Raman}
177 are the concentration of R6G for SERS spectra and the control analyte, respectively.

178 In prior of the acquisition of signals from Raman, suspension of *E. coli* cells was washed with
179 0.9% NaCl and Milli-Q water. The washed suspension of bacterial cells was pipetted on
180 microcapsules and then SERS measurements were made on dried samples.

181 Enhancement factors for bacterial (EFB) were calculated according to the formula:

$$EFB = \frac{I_{SERS}}{I_{Raman}} \cdot \frac{p_{Raman}}{p_{SERS}} \quad (2)$$

182 where I_{SERS} and I_{Raman} are intensities of the SERS amplified signal and initial signal of the control
183 bacteria; p_{SERS} and p_{Raman} are laser power for SERS spectra and control bacteria, respectively.

184 **2.8 Image analysis**

185 Analysis of SEM and Raman images was done by using ImageJ software
186 (<http://rsb.info.nih.gov/ij/>). SERS maps were chosen to count the capsules.

187

188 **3. Results and discussion**

189 The schematic of design and study of the inorganic Ag/Au capsules as SERS platform is
190 highlighted in Scheme 1. In the first step, calcium carbonate templates for microcapsules are
191 prepared. Calcium carbonate particles were chosen as templates because of their biocompatibility,
192 easiness of preparation and controllable size, shape. For preparation of calcium carbonate particle
193 templates, solutions containing the corresponding salts of CaCl_2 and Na_2CO_3 were poured into a
194 beaker upon rigorous steering to fabricate porous calcium carbonate cores. SEM analysis (scheme
195 1b, c) showed that the obtained vaterite particles ($4.01 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{m}$) with spherical shape contained
196 5 % of the calcite.

198 **Scheme 1.** Schematics of the experiment showing major steps employed for the preparation of all-
199 nanoparticle capsules.

200 In the next step, the formation of the nanoparticle shell was performed. For this purpose, AgNPs
201 and AuNPs were used, but they were prepared differently. AgNPs were obtained via an in-situ
202 synthesis named silver-mirror reaction. Based on SEM (scheme 1d, e) analysis, we obtained that
203 AgNPs with two main sizes ($0.09 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{m}$ and $0.20 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{m}$, $R^2=0.9823$) are present on the

204 surface, while the shape of both particles is almost spherical. This various size represent the
205 synthesis in a surface and the size of the particles are limited by the porous size which are 90 nm
206 of the calcium carbonate from other and number of the particles are formatted in solution and have
207 a larger size up to 250nm average 200 nm.[75,76]

208 Such an approach represents an easy way of directly coating the surfaces of capsules as it was
209 discussed earlier.[13] For an alternating layer in the LbL assembly, AuNPs were used. Although
210 there are many ways for preparation of AuNPs, having a high concentration of nanoparticles is
211 very important for an effective coverage of the surface of all particles.[77] That is why in the
212 synthesis of AuNPs with size 6 nm we have chosen a method of AuNPs with a high yield (i.e. high
213 concentrations) which are stabilized by 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP). After the
214 microcapsule assembly was complete, calcium carbonate templates on which the capsules formed
215 were removed by EDTA producing microcapsules with nanoparticle on the walls.

216 The bilayer of AgNPs and AuNPs covers the surface of calcium carbonate particles until the
217 core is completely covered with the increasing number of bilayers of AgNPs and AuNPs, as shown
218 in Figure 1a-e. Meanwhile, most walls of capsules with 4 layers were destroyed when the template
219 was removed, as it can be seen in Figure 1f. Note that the stable hollow microcapsule were obtained
220 with the minimum of 5 layers of nanoparticles, as it is shown in Figure 1g, h, i and j. 5 layers is
221 sufficient even though the gold particles are small (6 nm), they contribute to the shell stability as
222 well. SEM images (Figure S1) can also show that there is no significant difference between the
223 size of capsules with a diameter of approximately 4.1-4.3 μm ($4.11 \pm 0.96 \mu\text{m}$, $4.38 \pm 0.77 \mu\text{m}$,
224 $4.33 \pm 0.67 \mu\text{m}$, $4.28 \pm 0.61 \mu\text{m}$ depended on the structure) compared with the size of the initial
225 calcium carbonate cores $4.01 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{m}$.

226
 227 **Figure 1.** SEM images of calcium carbonate with adsorbed nanoparticles (top row a-e) and hollow
 228 capsules obtained after CaCO_3 dissolution (bottom row f-j) with different number of the metal
 229 nanoparticles layers: (a, f) 4 layers - $(\text{Ag}/\text{Au})\times 2$; (b, g) 5 layers - $(\text{Ag}/\text{Au})\times 2/\text{Ag}$; (c, h) 6 layers-
 230 $(\text{Ag}/\text{Au})\times 3$; (d, i) 7 layers - $(\text{Ag}/\text{Au})\times 3/\text{Ag}$ and (e, j) 8 layers - $(\text{Ag}/\text{Au})\times 4$.

231 The efficient dissolution of calcium carbonate template was proved by the X-Ray diffraction
 232 (XRD) (Figure 2) processed via the Rietveld analysis. The samples with CaCO_3 core inside (Figure
 233 2a) have one main peak (29.32°) assigned to the (104) plane and some feeble peaks, which
 234 correspond to calcite (CaCO_3) as well as the peak of silver and gold. All spectra of capsules with
 235 the dissolved CaCO_3 cores only have four main diffraction peaks at 38.03° , 44.20° , 64.29° , and
 236 77.20° could be assigned to (111), (200), (220), and (311) planes of AgNPs, respectively (Figure
 237 2b) and well-matched with the Database pdf4. It should be noted that the peaks at 38.05° , 44.22° ,
 238 64.32° and 77.24° could be also assigned to (111), (200), (220), and (311) planes of AuNPs (Figure
 239 2b), which are challenging to distinguish from those of AgNPs. In addition, it was noticed that the
 240 vaterite core converted to calcite, this can be assigned to a long synthesis process in an aqueous
 241 solution. There are no calcium carbonate peaks found on XRD spectra of all samples obtained after

242 calcium carbonate dissolution (Figure 2b), which means that microcapsules were formed only by
243 metal nanoparticles.

244
245 **Figure 2.** XRD diffraction spectra of (a) calcium carbonate core with adsorbed nanoparticles and
246 (b) hollow all nanoparticle microcapsules synthesized with different composite structures:
247 (Ag/Au)×2, (Ag/Au)×2/Ag, (Ag/Au)×3, (Ag/Au)×3/Ag, (Ag/Au)×4, respectively; where the red
248 and green dash lines indicate silver/gold and calcite (C), respectively.

249 The SERS capability of Au/Ag microcapsules were tested by measuring R6G as a model analyte.
250 The mechanism of adsorption of this molecule is the physical sorption on the surface of the
251 scaffold. As the hollow microcapsules only could be obtained with at least 5 layers of
252 nanoparticles, the effect of the concentrations of R6G on the SERS sensitivity Au/Ag
253 microcapsules with 6 layers and 8 layers both were measured.

254 Prior acquiring SERS spectra, microcapsules were incubated in solution of R6G at different
255 concentrations of 10⁻³, 10⁻⁴, 10⁻⁵ M for 20 min. Typically, R6G has the most intensive fingerprint
256 peaks located at 1308 cm⁻¹, 1357 cm⁻¹, 1506 cm⁻¹ representing the C-C aromatic stretching of the

257 dye (R6G), as it is shown in Figure 3. Peaks appearing in the spectrum at 1178 cm^{-1} and 795 cm^{-1}
258 are due to the in-plane and out-plane bending of C–H, respectively, while the band at 1076 cm^{-1}
259 can be assigned to residual calcium carbonate (Figure 3a).

260 To evaluate the efficiency of these microcapsules as a SERS platform, an analytical enhancement
261 factor (EF) was calculated by applying eq 1 based on the intensity of the most intensive peak of
262 1506 cm^{-1} (Figure 3b). The microcapsules fabricated with AuNPs as the outermost layer only
263 demonstrate amplification up to than 20 folds properties. This issue could be due to the organic
264 stabilizer surrounding on AuNPs decrease the local conductivity of the metallic surface.

265
266 **Figure 3.** SERS spectra (a) and EF (b) based on the intensity of the peak of 1506 cm^{-1} for varying
267 concentrations (10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , and 10^{-5} M) of R6G adsorbed by microcapsules with the shell
268 comprising of $(\text{Ag}/\text{Au})\times 4$. The mean value of the EF is shown near the corresponding boxes. Laser
269 power: 120 mW.

270 To prove this concept, we studied the EF of 7 layer capsules possessing the following structure
271 $(\text{Ag}/\text{Au})\times 3/\text{Ag}$ with non-stabilized AgNPs as the outermost layer. These microcapsules showed a

272 significant increase of amplification signals up to 10^7 at the lowest laser power (0.05 mW), as it is
273 shown in Fig. 4a. It can be noted that two outliers appear when the laser power is 0.1 and 0.5 mW
274 at the concentration of R6G of 10^{-4} M. These suggests that so-called “hot spots” contribute to the
275 SERS signals enormously. We further calculated an enhancement factor based on the Raman
276 intensity at 1506 cm^{-1} for all imaged areas ($3*3=9$ points), as shown in Fig. 4b. The EF calculated
277 from three independent scanned area (Fig. 4b) could be seen on the scanned maps. EF did not show
278 significant variation in the scanned area.

279 Such high amplification can be explained by the structure of the microcapsules shell that all
280 nanoparticles of the in the shell touch each other. In this case, the optimal distance between
281 nanoparticles and conductivity could be provided.[78,79]

282

283

284

285 **Figure 4.** (a) EF of R6G adsorbed by microcapsules with shell of (Ag/Au) \times 3/Ag calculated on the
286 different laser power (0.05 mW – 1 mW) showing a value range of 10^4 - 10^7 . The left group was
287 measured with R6G of 10^{-3} M, and right was measured with R6G of 10^{-4} M. Two pots out of the
288 box are outliers. (b) EF map of R6G adsorbed by microcapsules with shell of (Ag/Au) \times 3/Ag from
289 were calculated based on acquiring the Raman intensity and eq 1 at 1506 cm^{-1} from three
290 independent areas (column from left to right) highlighted with the red square in optical microscopy
291 images (bottom row) with various laser power (0.1 mW, 0.5 mW and 1 mW).

292 SERS detection of bacteria using microcapsules

293 For demonstrate the proof of principal using designed contains in biomedicine for detect the
294 microorganisms such as bacteria we used model organism the *E. coli* strain. The SERS spectra for
295 different power of laser (Fig. 5). Bacterial Raman spectra (blue line) shown in Fig. 5 consist of
296 bands representing the cell contents, primarily proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, and nucleic
297 acids.[80] For example, strong Raman peaks located at 1000 and 1659 cm^{-1} were assigned to

298 proteins,[81,82]; the peak at 1446 cm^{-1} was assigned to carbohydrates or lipids,[81,82] 1029; and
299 1128 cm^{-1} have been previously attributed to carbohydrates,[82,83] 721 cm^{-1} corresponds to
300 nucleic acids[82,83]. Table 1 shows the main Raman peaks of the three spectra and the tentative
301 assignment for the most relevant bands. It is observed that there is a significant SERS enhancement
302 at different laser power and a clear trend of variation of enhancement with increase in the laser
303 power between the range of $1000\text{-}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in Fig. 5 (red and green line), while SERS
304 enhancements did not present enormous difference in this range.

305 On the other hand, there were more vibrational bands observed in SERS spectra of *E. coli*, which
306 depend on the power of laser. For example, peaks at 1190 , 1399 , 1503 cm^{-1} appear only in the
307 SERS spectra, can result in the high SERS signals. To use such platform to detect bacterial cells,
308 it is essential to estimate the enhancement factor for SERS signals. In this case, we used eq 2 based
309 on the most intensive SERS peak present at 1446 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to the CH_2 and CH_3
310 vibrations of proteins and lipids to count the EFB. The enhancement factor of *E. coli* was measured
311 to be up to 7.8×10^4 and 2.8×10^3 with laser power of 1.5 mW and 5 mW , respectively.

312 **Table 1** Assignments of SERS signatures of *Escherichia coli* acquired from microcapsules and
 313 Raman bands of *Escherichia coli* taken from bacteria suspension in water based on recent
 314 literature. [80,82,84–88]

Peak position (cm ⁻¹)			Chemical groups assignment
Raman	SERS		
87 mW	1.5 mW	5 mW	
	621	619	CC twisting—tryptophan
	648	648	Tyrosine
	684	673	Valine
	706	710	Calcium Carbonate
	731	733	Adenine ring stretching; peptidoglycan
	749	749	Tryptophan
	781	781	Cytosine, uracil (ring stretching)
	796	799	C–O–P–O–C—RNA binding
825	842		Tyrosine
	878	874	CCH deformation (Agar)
	938	932	C–C stretching (amide III)—protein
	964	964	CCH deformation (Agar)
1000	988	988	C–C skeletal stretching of aromatic ring—phenylalanine/tyrosine
	1021		Bacteria metabolism (?)
	1056		Carbohydrates
1095	1083	1090	Nucleic acids (PO ₂ —symmetrical stretching); C–C and C–O–C skeletal stretching—glycosidic linkage of saccharides
1121	1155		carbohydrates
	1190	1200	Amide III; C–C tyrosine stretching, phenylalanine, tryptophan (protein)
1248	1239	1248	C–N e N–H stretching (amide III); thymine and adenine (ring breathing); CH ₂ lipids deformation; saccharides
1316	1281	1280	C–N and N–H stretching (amide III); CH ₂ and CH ₃ —protein deformation; guanine breathing ring
1330	1345	1355	CH ₂ and CH ₃ —fatty acids and protein deformation; N–H stretching (amide III); C–C stretching—tryptophan; adenine, guanine (ring breathing)
	1399	1396	–COO– symmetric and asymmetric stretching—peptidoglycan
1446	1427	1435	CH ₂ and CH ₃ deformations—lipids and proteins
	1503	1506	–C–C conjugated stretching—carotenoids
	1533	1557	Tryptophan; exopolysaccharides
	1598	1603	C–C ring stretching—phenylalanine, tyrosine and tryptophan
1659	1625	1654	C–O stretching (amide I); C–C stretching—lipids

315

316

317 **Figure 5.** (a) SERS spectra of *E. coli* TOP10 obtained from microcapsules (blue). Normal Raman
 318 spectrum of *E. coli*; (purple) and (green) are SERS spectra of *E. coli* immobilized on microcapsules
 319 with laser power 5 mW and 1.5 mW, respectively.

320 In recent years, structural fabrication by nanoarchitectonics corresponds to the creation of a
 321 rising tide in material design. Nanoarchitectonics has begun to spread into many fields and became
 322 a common and basic concept, as seen in various applications such as nanostructured materials,
 323 supramolecular assemblies, hybrid materials, fabrication methodologies.[89] LbL assemblies of
 324 inorganic particle hybrid onto porous CaCO₃ particles achieved in this work and another
 325 nanoarchitectonics-based work[30] by high precision deposition of alternating stacks of SiO₂ and
 326 more densely packed TiO₂ nanoparticles are both using the cost-effective LbL process and opens
 327 up possibilities in numerous technologically relevant applications.

328 Conclusions

329 Novel LbL inorganic microcapsules are designed using alternative adsorption of the gold
 330 nanoparticles and in situ synthesis of the silver nanoparticles as layers. It is found in our work that
 331 5 layers of metal nanoparticles is the minimum number of layers to form a stable shell. Such hollow

332 capsules keep the same spherical shape and size $4.25 \pm 0.82 \mu\text{m}$. The microcapsules are found to
333 be efficient SERS substrates for a label-free detection of Rhodamine 6G. All types of the capsules
334 reveal high enhancement factors in range of 10^6 - 10^7 . The proof of principal of using such capsules
335 for microorganism detection was shown by the bacteria immobilization on the particles surface.
336 We demonstrate that the microcapsules provide sensitivity and 13 additional peaks related to the
337 bacteria composition have been detected as well the enhancement of the major bacteria's peak
338 $10^4/10^9$. We foresee that developed approaches would be feasible for the rapid diagnostics and
339 discrimination of microorganisms particularly bacterial cells, which remains one of the most
340 challenged tasks in health care, clinical, environmental, food field.

341 **Appendix A. Supplementary material**

342 Supplementary material.

343 **Author Contributions**

344 J.L. conducted research and wrote the manuscript, J.L. and D.K. conducted Raman
345 measurements, A.L. contribute to bacteria experiments, D.V. contributed with working out the
346 concept, B.V.P. supervised this work, A.G.S. supervised this work. All authors contributed to
347 writing.

348 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

349 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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Supporting Information

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Surface enhanced Raman scattering (SERS)

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enhancement by layer-by-layer (LbL) assembly all-

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nanoparticle microcapsules

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Fig. S1. Size of microcapsules with different layers of shell.

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